

ANALYSIS OF MICRO/MESO/MACRO TEMPERATURE-DEPENDENT ELASTOVISCOPLASTIC PROPERTIES OF WOVEN COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In this study, temperature dependence of elastoviscoplastic behavior of plain-woven glass fiber-reinforced plastic (GFRP) composites is experimentally observed, and the behavior is analyzed using a triple-scale homogenization analysis method. In the triple-scale homogenization method, first, an analysis model is defined, in which a plain-woven composite is regarded as a macro-structure, plain fabrics and a matrix as a meso-structure, fibers and a matrix in a fiber bundle as a micro-structure. Tensile tests of a plain-woven glass fiber/epoxy GFRP composite are conducted under several temperature and strain rate conditions, showing its strong dependence on temperature. Based on the experimental results, temperature-dependent elastoviscoplastic parameters of the epoxy are identified. Using the obtained parameters and the triple-scale homogenization method, elastoviscoplastic behavior of the plain-woven GFRP composite subjected to on-axis (0° , 90°) or off-axis (15° , 30° , 45°) loading is analyzed at several temperature conditions. It is found that the elastoviscoplastic properties of the plain-woven GFRP composite significantly depend on the temperature conditions and loading directions. It is also shown that the analysis results are in good agreement with the experimental data in various temperature conditions and loading directions.

1 INTRODUCTION

Woven composites consisting of fabrics and matrix materials have been used in many industrial fields such as aerospace, automobile and energy-related industries, because of their high specific stiffness and strength. From such backgrounds, plain-woven composites can be exposed to various temperature environments, and in such cases, characteristics of composites change nonlinearly due to the temperature-dependent properties of resin materials in the composites. Therefore, it is very important to analyze the change of mechanical properties of woven composites depending on temperature.

Figure 1: Triple-scale model of plain-woven composites.

Woven composites can be modelled in three scales as illustrated in Fig.1. In this modeling, the meso-structure consisting of fiber bundles (yarns) and a matrix in the composites, and the micro-structure consisting of fibers and a matrix in the yarns, can be assumed to have periodic structures, respectively. The mathematical homogenization method [1] is one of the most useful methods to analyze the properties of materials having periodic internal structures. Our research group has developed the triple-scale homogenization method [2] based on the homogenization theory for nonlinear time-dependent composites [3] for plain-woven composites. In this method, we are able to explicitly take into account elastoviscoplastic properties of matrix materials to obtain micro/meso/macro elastoviscoplastic properties of woven composites. Therefore, if we incorporate temperature-dependent properties of matrix materials in the method, it can be possible to analyze temperature-dependent elastoviscoplastic properties of woven composites. However, so far no such analysis has been done.

In this study, first, we experimentally examine the temperature dependence of elastoviscoplastic behavior of plain-woven glass fiber-reinforced plastic (GFRP) composites. Furthermore, elastoviscoplastic analysis considering temperature dependence of plain-woven GFRP composites are carried out based on the triple-scale homogenization method.

2 TRIPLE-SCALE HOMOGENIZATION METHOD FOR PLAIN-WOVEN COMPOSITES

For the analysis, a plain-woven composite is defined in three scales as illustrated in Fig. 1. Then, a basic cell A consisting of yarns and a matrix is defined as a smallest unit in the meso-scale. Cartesian coordinates x_i ($i=1, 2, 3$) are provided for the meso-scale. In the micro-scale, a semiunit cell B consisting of a fiber and a matrix is defined as a smallest unit for the yarn region A_y in A . Cartesian coordinates y_i ($i=1, 2, 3$) are provided for the micro-scale.

Microscopic stress and strain rate in B are denoted as ${}^2\dot{\sigma}_{ij}$ and ${}^2\dot{\epsilon}_{kl}$, respectively, where ${}^2(\)$ indicates that the variables are with respect to the micro-scale, and the elastic stiffness and viscoplastic strain rate of fibers and a matrix are denoted as ${}^2c_{ijkl}$ and ${}^2\beta_{kl}$, respectively, ${}^2\chi_i^{kl}$ and ${}^2\varphi_i$ are the characteristic functions obtained by solving the boundary value problems in the micro-scale. Using these functions, the evolution equation of ${}^2\dot{\sigma}_{ij}$ is expressed as [2]

$${}^2\dot{\sigma}_{ij} = {}^2c_{ijkl} (\delta_{pk} \delta_{ql} + {}^2\chi_{p,y_q}) {}^1\dot{\epsilon}_{kl} - {}^2c_{ijkl} ({}^2\beta_{kl} - {}^2\varphi_{k,y_l}), \quad (1)$$

where $(\)_{,y_i}$ stands for the differentiation with respect to y_i , and ${}^1(\)$ indicates that the variables are with respect to the meso-scale. Then, the relation between mesoscopic stress and strain rates, ${}^1\dot{\sigma}_{ij}$ and ${}^1\dot{\epsilon}_{kl}$ is derived as follows[2]:

$${}^1\dot{\sigma}_{ij} = \left\langle {}^2c_{ijkl} (\delta_{pk} \delta_{ql} + {}^2\chi_{p,y_q}) \right\rangle_B {}^1\dot{\epsilon}_{kl} - \left\langle {}^2c_{ijkl} ({}^2\beta_{kl} - {}^2\varphi_{k,y_l}) \right\rangle_B, \quad (2)$$

where $\langle \ \rangle_B$ designates the volume average in B .

Similarly, by applying the homogenization theory to the meso/macro-scale, the evolution equation of ${}^1\dot{\sigma}_{ij}$ and the relation between macroscopic stress and strain rates, ${}^0\dot{\sigma}_{ij}$ and ${}^0\dot{\epsilon}_{kl}$, are respectively derived as follows [2]:

$${}^1\dot{\sigma}_{ij} = {}^1c_{ijkl} (\delta_{pk} \delta_{ql} + {}^1\chi_{p,x_q}) {}^0\dot{\epsilon}_{kl} - {}^1c_{ijkl} ({}^1\beta_{kl} - {}^1\varphi_{k,x_l}), \quad (3)$$

$${}^0\dot{\sigma}_{ij} = \left\langle {}^1c_{ijkl} (\delta_{pk} \delta_{ql} + {}^1\chi_{p,x_q}) \right\rangle_A {}^0\dot{\epsilon}_{kl} - \left\langle {}^1c_{ijkl} ({}^1\beta_{kl} - {}^1\varphi_{k,x_l}) \right\rangle_A, \quad (4)$$

where ${}^1c_{ijkl}$ and ${}^1\beta_{kl}$ respectively represent the elastic stiffness and viscoplastic strain rate of yarns and a matrix, ${}^1\chi_i^{kl}$ and ${}^1\varphi_i$ are the characteristic functions obtained by solving the boundary value problems in the meso-scale, ${}^0(\)$ indicates that the variables are with respect to the macro-scale, $(\)_{,x_i}$ stands for the differentiation with respect to x_i , and $\langle \ \rangle_A$ designates the volume average in A . Then, the elastic stiffness ${}^1c_{ijkl}$ and the viscoplastic strain rate ${}^1\beta_{kl}$ of yarns were the following relations in A_y obtained from Eq. (2)

$${}^1c_{ijkl} = \left\langle {}^2c_{ijkl} (\delta_{ik} \delta_{jl} + {}^2\chi_{i,y_j}^{kl}) \right\rangle_B \text{ in } A_y, \quad (5)$$

$${}^1c_{ijkl} {}^1\beta_{kl} = \left\langle {}^2c_{ijkl} ({}^2\beta_{kl} - {}^2\varphi_{k,y_l}) \right\rangle_B \text{ in } A_y. \quad (6)$$

Using these relations, the elastoviscoplastic behavior of plain-woven composites can be analyzed through the three scales.

3 IDENTIFICATION OF TEMPERATURE-DEPENDENT ELASTOVISCOPLASTIC PARAMETERS OF EPOXY MATRIX

3.1 Test specimen and test method

To examine temperature-dependent elastoviscoplastic parameters of epoxy matrix, a PGE-6635 glass fiber/epoxy plain-woven composite (1000×1000×2 mm, 12 plain fabrics stacked) was prepared. Then, with reference to JIS K 7165, strip-shaped test specimens (250×25×2 mm) were cut out. The cutting angle was 45° off-axis because viscoplastic properties and temperature dependence of the epoxy appeared most remarkably at 45° tension. Aluminum tabs (50×25×2 mm) were adhered on the grips of the specimens to prevent breakage due to tightening of clamps and to obtain accurate stress-strain relationships at the center of the specimens. To measure strain, biaxial strain gauges were attached at the center of both sides of the specimens. In addition, a uniaxial strain gauge for strain control was also attached on one side.

The tensile tests were performed using a universal tensile testing machine equipped with a load/strain controller. The strain rate in the loading direction was fixed at 10^{-3} s^{-1} or 10^{-5} s^{-1} . The number of tests for each strain rate was $n \geq 2$. Temperature conditions were four kinds, i.e. room temperature (25°C), 60°C, 80°C and 100°C. In the tests of high temperature conditions, an electric thermostatic chamber was used, and the temperature was controlled to be constant. The tests were started after the temperature in the chamber reached target temperature, and then the temperature was held constant for 30 minutes to conduct the tests with uniform temperature distribution in the specimens and jigs.

3.2 Identification of temperature-dependent elastoviscoplastic parameters of epoxy

Temperature-dependent elastoviscoplastic parameters of the epoxy were identified using the stress-strain relationships of the plain-woven GFRP composite at each temperature obtained by the experiments and the triple-scale homogenization method described in Section 2. In this study, the glass fibers were regarded as isotropic elastic materials (temperature-independent), and the epoxy was regarded as an isotropic elastoviscoplastic material (temperature-dependent) obeying the following constitutive equation:

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_{ij} = \frac{1 + \nu_m}{E_m} \dot{\sigma}_{ij} - \frac{\nu_m}{E_m} \dot{\sigma}_{kk} \delta_{ij} + \frac{3}{2} \dot{\varepsilon}_0 \left[\frac{\sigma_{eq}}{g(\bar{\varepsilon}^p)} \right]^n \frac{s_{ij}}{\sigma_{eq}}, \quad (7)$$

where E_m , ν_m and n are the Young's modulus, the Poisson's ratio and the viscoplastic nonlinear power coefficient of the epoxy, respectively, $g(\bar{\varepsilon}^p)$ is the hardening function depending on the equivalent plastic strain, $\dot{\varepsilon}_0$ and s_{ij} denote the reference strain rate and the deviating stress, respectively. The hardening function was set as shown below:

$$g(\bar{\varepsilon}^p) = A(\bar{\varepsilon}^p)^B + C, \quad (8)$$

where A , B and C are material constants which were considered to be temperature-dependent. These temperature-dependent parameters of the epoxy were identified by fitting the stress-strain relations at each temperature obtained by the tensile tests. They are shown in Table 1. Subsequently, function approximation of the five temperature-dependent parameters in Table 1 was performed associated with temperature change. In this research, the Kohlraush-Williams-Watts (KWW) function [4] was used as a function to approximate the parameters. The approximate functions obtained are as follows:

$$E_m(T) = -3.3 \exp\left\{-(T/360)^{-29}\right\} + 3.5, \quad (9)$$

$$n(T) = -26.8 \exp\left\{-(T/338)^{-27}\right\} + 31, \quad (10)$$

$$A(T) = -108 \exp\left\{-(T/354)^{-13}\right\} + 102, \quad (11)$$

$$B(T) = 0.7 \exp\left\{-(T/373)^{-22}\right\} + 0.31, \quad (12)$$

$$C(T) = -40.8 \exp\left\{-(T/321)^{-7.9}\right\} + 1.7, \quad (13)$$

where, T represents the absolute temperature.

4 TRIPLE-SCALE ELASTOVISCOPLASTIC ANALYSIS OF PLAIN-WOVEN GFRP COMPOSITE

4.1 Analysis conditions

In the present analysis, elastoviscoplastic behavior of the plain-woven GFRP composite was analyzed using the proposed theory. As a meso-scale model, the basic cell *A* with 70% yarn volume fraction was defined as shown in Fig. 2(a), and divided into eight-node isoparametric elements (1888 elements, 2329 nodes). On the other hand, as a micro-scale model, the semiunit cell *B* with 72% fiber volume fraction was defined as shown in Fig. 3, and divided into four-node isoparametric elements (81 elements, 91 nodes) by assuming the generalized plain strain condition. Micro-scale variables were

Table 1: Temperature-dependent parameters of epoxy.

Temp.[°C]	E_m [MPa]	n	A [MPa]	B	C [MPa]
25	3.50×10^3	31	100	0.3	25
60	3.45×10^3	25	90	0.32	12
80	2.90×10^3	11	65	0.35	7
100	1.20×10^3	6	37	0.58	3.2

Table 2: Material constants.

Young's modulus of glass fiber	E_f [GPa]	80.0
Poisson's ratio of epoxy	ν_m	0.35
Poisson's ratio of glass fiber	ν_f	0.22
Reference strain rate	$\dot{\epsilon}_0$ [1/s]	1.0×10^{-5}

Figure 2: Finite element mesh of plain-woven GFRP composite; (a) full view and (b) yarns.

Figure 3: Semiunit cell *B* and finite element mesh.

Figure 4: Evaluation points of micro-scale variables in yarns.

examined at the integral points shown in Fig. 4. The temperature-dependent elastoviscoplastic parameters of the epoxy are already shown in Section 3, and the material constants of glass fibers and other material constants are shown in Table 2. The plain-woven composite was subjected to the uniaxial load in the direction rotated from the x_3 -direction with θ in the x_1-x_3 plane at 25°C, 80°C and 100°C. Five loading directions were considered, i.e. $\theta=0^\circ, 15^\circ, 30^\circ, 45^\circ, 90^\circ$. A constant strain rate of ${}^0\dot{\varepsilon}_\theta=10^{-5}\text{s}^{-1}$ was applied until the macroscopic strain reached 1.5%. Furthermore, we conducted tensile tests under the same conditions as in the analysis, and confirmed validity of our method.

4.2 Results of analysis

Figure 5 show the macroscopic stress-strain relations using the triple-scale homogenization analysis (solid lines) and the experimental results (plots) at room temperature and 100°C, respectively. From these figures, the experimental results and the analysis results are in good agreement, showing the validity of the present method. Furthermore, it can be seen that while the on-axis load shows linear behavior, the off-axis load shows remarkable nonlinear behavior. Comparing the results at room temperature and 100°C, the beginning of nonlinear deformation at 100°C is earlier and the macroscopic stress decreases.

Figures 6 and 7 show the distribution of mesoscopic equivalent stress and viscoplastic strain in the basic cell A with $\theta=0^\circ$ at room temperature when the macroscopic strain is 1.0%. Figures 8 and 9 show the distribution of mesoscopic equivalent stress and viscoplastic strain in A with $\theta=45^\circ$ at room

Figure 5: Macroscopic stress-strain relations; (a) room temperature and (b) 100°C.

Figure 6: Distribution of mesoscopic equivalent stress ($T=25^\circ\text{C}$, $\theta=0^\circ$); (a) full view and (b) yarns.

Figure 7: Distribution of mesoscopic equivalent strain ($T=25^\circ\text{C}$, $\theta=0^\circ$); (a) full view and (b) yarns.

temperature when the macroscopic strain is 1.0%. As shown in Figs. 6 and 7, high equivalent stress is observed in the yarns, while large equivalent strain is observed in the epoxy. On the other hand, it can be seen from Figs. 8 and 9 that large equivalent stress occurs at the fiber bundle in the x_1 -direction, and that equivalent viscoplastic strain is larger than that at 0° tension.

Finally, Figs. 10 and 11 show the distributions of microscopic equivalent stress and viscoplastic strain in the semiunit cell B at the integral points (i)-(vi) with $\theta=0^\circ$ at room temperature. As seen from the figures, high equivalent stress occurs in the fibers especially at the point (i), (ii) and (iii), while large equivalent viscoplastic strain takes place in the epoxy especially at the point (i). Such microscopic stress and strain in the yarns are able to be investigated using the present method.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we experimentally observed temperature-dependent elastoviscoplastic behavior of a plain-woven GFRP composite, and performed elastoviscoplastic analysis of the composite under

Figure 8: Distribution of mesoscopic equivalent stress ($T=25^\circ\text{C}$, $\theta=45^\circ$); (a) full view and (b) yarns.

Figure 9: Distribution of mesoscopic equivalent strain ($T=25^\circ\text{C}$, $\theta=45^\circ$); (a) full view and (b) yarns.

Figure 10: Distribution of microscopic equivalent stress ($T=25^\circ\text{C}$, $\theta=0^\circ$).

Figure 11: Distribution of microscopic equivalent strain ($T=25^\circ\text{C}$, $\theta=0^\circ$).

various temperature environments based on the triple-scale homogenization method. Temperature-dependent elastoviscoplastic parameters of an epoxy matrix were identified by fitting the results of tensile tests, and the parameters were used for the analysis of the plain-woven GFRP composite. We also conducted experiments under the same conditions as the analysis, and verified the validity of the present analysis method.

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